

Studies on the Kinetics and Mechanism of Interaction of α -Amino Acids with Ninhydrin

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Kinetic studies of α -amino acids with ninhydrin suggests that the formation of purple colour, ammonia and hydrindantin follow a complex reaction path consisting parallel reactions. Purple colour and evolution of ammonia follows the pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate constants increase with increasing pH upto pH 5.0, beyond which no measurable reaction is observed. The effects of temperature, pH, oxygen and organic solvents (methyl cellosolve and dimethyl sulphoxide) on the reaction rate are discussed. The proposed mechanism for the formation of purple colour, ammonia and hydrindantin, confirms the observed results.

THE use of ninhydrin for the detection and quantitative estimation of α -amino acids depends on the formation of purple colour¹. The mechanism of this important reaction has been the subject matter of numerous investigations². The survey of the literature on the α -amino acids-ninhydrin reaction reveals that the previous mechanisms are not supported by the systematic kinetic studies. In the communication, a detailed study of the kinetics and mechanism of the formation of purple colour and evolution of ammonia is reported.

Experimental

Glycine, alanine, phenylalanine, asparagine and serine (all B.D.H.) were used as such. Solutions of amino acids and ninhydrin (B.D.H.) were prepared in McIlvaine buffer at different pH. pH measurements were made using a Elico LI-10 pH meter.

The requisite solutions of amino acids except ninhydrin were thermostated in an oil-bath to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The reaction was then started by adding the requisite volume of ninhydrin. The ionic strength was maintained with potassium nitrate solution. Pure nitrogen gas was bubbled through the reaction mixture. The progress of the reaction was followed spectrophotometrically by pipetting aliquotes at different time intervals and measuring the optical density at 575 nm using a Bousch & Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer.

The rate of evolution of ammonia was studied in pH range 3-6 under similar conditions as described for the purple colour formation. Ammonia was estimated by the reported method³.

The studies on the kinetics and mechanism of the interaction of α -amino acids with ninhydrin under various experimental conditions are associated with the following facts. The evolution of carbon dioxide is very fast and is complete within

few minutes at 70° while the formation of purple colour is negligible within this time interval. The maximum development of the colour is in the vicinity of pH 5.0. The colour development is dependent on the temperature of the reaction mixture. In the vicinity of 40° , the colour development is very faint but as the temperature is increased, the colour increases and reaches a maximum value at about 95° . In presence of oxygen the colour yield is very low. Alongwith colour development by the interaction of α -amino acids with ninhydrin, there is evolution of ammonia which also reacts with ninhydrin to give the purple colour. Hydrindantin is also formed during the colour development.

The pseudo-first order rate constants for purple colour were calculated at different ninhydrin concentration, temperature and pH. The effect of temperature was studied under nitrogen atmosphere. The plots of optical density versus time for different temperature are shown in Fig. 1. The formation

Fig. 1. Plots of optical density of Ruhemann's purple vs time for reaction of glycine with ninhydrin at various temperatures; pH = 5.0.

of purple colour was found to increase with temperature and reached a stationary state at a given temperature which shows that there is an equilibrium step which governed the rate constant. The activation parameters were also calculated using the Arrhenius and Eyring equations (Table 1). The

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR FORMATION OF PURPLE COLOUR

[Amino acid] = 1.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, pH = 5.0, [Ninhydrin] = 0.025 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 80°, ionic strength = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

Amino acid	k_{obs} min ⁻¹	$E_a^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Glycine	4.49×10^{-5}	73.86	70.42	-50.90
Alanine	4.48×10^{-5}	73.26	70.92	54.71
Phenylalanine	4.50×10^{-5}	73.30	70.37	51.02
Asparagine	4.47×10^{-5}	73.31	70.37	51.04
Serine	4.48×10^{-5}	73.23	70.80	51.11

effect of pH was studied over the range 2.2–6.0. At pH 2.2–4.0 the colour is not formed. As the pH is increased from 4.0 to 4.5, colour develops but is not stable and optimum pH for stable colour formation is found between 5 and 6 in nitrogen atmosphere.

On the basis of these results and previous observations, the mechanism is presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

α -Amino acid reacts with ninhydrin to give carbondioxide, aldehyde and 2-aminoindandione which is a stable intermediate. It acts as a reactant for the colour formation and evolution of ammonia. 2-Aminoindandione participates in two parallel reactions. In one case, it reacts with ninhydrin to give 2-hydroxyindandione and 2-iminoindandione which condense to produce purple colour. In the second case, 2-aminoindandione in presence of hydronium ion, hydrolyses to give ammonia and hydrindantin.

On the basis of this mechanism the following rate equation has been derived for the formation of purple colour,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_{eq} k_2 K_a [B]}{[H^+]} \quad (1)$$

According to the above rate equation the rate constant should vary directly with ninhydrin concentration and inversely as the hydrogen ion concentration. This is confirmed from the plots of k_{obs} vs ninhydrin concentration (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Dependence of pseudo-first order rate constant (purple colour formation) on [Ninhydrin] for the reaction of amino acids at pH = 5.0 and temp. = 80°: (1) gly, (2) ala, (3) phe, (4) asp, and (5) ser. The origin has been shifted on the X-axis by one cm for each amino acid.

The evolution of ammonia from α -amino acid – ninhydrin reaction increased on increasing the pH from 2.2 to 5.0. It was negligible above pH 5.0 due to the formation of stable purple colour. The ammonia was converted into ammonium ions in the acidic medium and it was swept out by a constant current of nitrogen gas. Evolution of ammonia also follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The effect of temperature on evolution of ammonia was studied over the range 70–95°. The various

activation parameters were determined by using Arrhenius and Eyring equations (Table 2).

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR EVOLUTION OF AMMONIA

[Amino acid] = 1.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [Ninhydrin] = 0.025 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 80°, pH = 5.0

Amino acid	k_{obs} min ⁻¹	$E_a^{\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^{\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^{\ddagger}$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Glycolne	6.47×10^{-4}	67.01	64.07	-64.82
Alanine	6.58×10^{-4}	67.62	64.68	-64.94
Phenylalanine	6.90×10^{-4}	67.32	64.38	-64.77
Asparagine	6.47×10^{-4}	67.62	64.68	-64.95
Serine	5.92×10^{-4}	68.89	65.96	-63.78

On the basis of the mechanism for the hydrolysis of 2-aminoindandione (Scheme 1), the following rate equation has been derived.

$$\frac{d[\text{NH}_4^+]}{dt} = \frac{k_1[\text{A}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{K_b} \quad (2)$$

It is clear from equation (2) that the rate of hydrolysis of 2-aminoindandione directly depends upon the hydrogen ion concentration.

Formation of hydrindantin, from α -amino acid – ninhydrin reaction is also found to be pH-dependent. Hydrindantin is deposited in reaction vessel below pH-4.0 because it is highly insoluble in water and was characterised by its spectra. Addition of hydrindantin in reaction mixture required the addition of organic solvents (methyl cellosolve and dimethyl sulphoxide) which kept it in solution during the course of reaction. It gives ninhydrin and 2-hydroxyindandione on hydrolysis which are responsible for the enhancement of rate of colour formation. Effect of methyl cellosolve and dimethyl sulphoxide is also explained on the basis of the solubility of hydrindantin in these organic solvents.

On the basis of the above discussion, it is concluded that the formation of purple colour, ammonia and hydrindantin are taking place through parallel reaction paths. The ratio of the concentration of purple colour to that of ammonia at any time would equal k_1/k_2 if no other complications are present. In this reaction 2-hydroxyindandione simultaneously reacts with ninhydrin to give hydrindantin, so that the total amount of purple colour that has been found from the α -amino acid – ninhydrin reaction at any time is equal to the sum of the

hydrindantin present in the reaction mixture. Therefore, at any given time,

$$k_1/k_2 = \frac{[\text{Purple colour}] + [\text{Hydrindantin}]}{[\text{Ammonia}]} \quad (3)$$

where, k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants for the formation of purple colour and evolution of ammonia respectively.

Formation of a molecule of hydrindantin is tied to the formation of one less molecule of purple colour. Thus one would expect the use of purple colour as a quantitative measure of amino acid content to be highly irreproducible, paralleling and irreproducible quantities of hydrindantin. In the presence of oxygen gas, there is no development of purple colour which shows that 2-aminoindandione in presence of oxygen undergoes other side-reaction⁴. On the other hand, 2-hydroxyindandione also undergoes rapid air-oxidation into ninhydrin⁵. Therefore, there is no possibilities for the formation of purple colour, ammonia and hydrindantin in presence of oxygen.

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